

Supplementary Information 2

Figure SI.2.1. Clustering tree for species basing on REGE analysis for Barents Sea food web.

Figure SI.2.2. Clustering tree for species basing on REGE analysis for Prince William Sound food web.

Figure SI.2.3. Clustering tree for species basing on REGE analysis for Carpinteria Salt Marsh food web.

Figure SI.2.4. Clustering tree for species basing on REGE analysis for Grande de Gredos food web.

Figure SI.2.5. Aggregated Barents Sea food web basing on REGE analysis.

Figure SI.2.6. Aggregated Prince William Sound food web basing on REGE analysis.

Figure SI.2.7. Aggregated Carpinteria Salt Marsh food web basing on REGE analysis.

Figure SI.2.8. Aggregated Grande de Gredos food web basing on REGE analysis.

